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ACCESS WITHOUT EQUITY? STAKEHOLDER PERSPECTIVES ON GHANA'S FREE SHS POLICY AND THE POLITICS OF EDUCATIONAL JUSTICE

Abstract

Ghana's Free Senior High School (FSHS) policy was implemented in 2017 with the goal of abolishing financial barriers to education and creating equity. This paper examined the policy's success through Nancy Fraser's framework of redistribution, recognition, and representation. The authors utilized interviews and focus groups from northern Ghana to evaluate the FSHS policy's success. This research found overall access improved, but there are still many systemic issues limiting the intended impact of policy. There were gaps in resources, a lack of girls and students with disabilities experiencing FSHS, and a lack of overall community participation. While access is important to educational justice, the study concludes access is not enough for educational justice and offered recommendations to achieve equity. Educational equity goes beyond access; it requires the involvement of diverse stakeholders in decision-making, targeted and responsive resources, and structural change to ensure all students access the supports they need to thrive.

Keywords: Free SHS Policy, Educational Equity, Access, Redistribution, Recognition, Representation

1. Introduction

Education is an increasingly acknowledged fundamental human right, as well as a necessary means for social and economic change (UNESCO, 2015; Sen, 1999). The importance of education at the secondary level is especially acknowledged to help reduce poverty, promote civic engagement, and support gender equity in countries like Ghana (Cooke et al., 2016; Lewin, 2009).

Since Ghana's independence in 1957, the country has experienced many reforms in education, but access, quality, and equity, especially at the Senior High School (SHS) level, continue to be problematic. The issues of access to secondary school are often indicative of structural inequalities related to socioeconomic class, locality, and unequal access to public services. The struggles have disproportionately impacted students who reside in rural areas, especially girls, and students with disabilities (Akyeampong, 2009; Rolleston, 2011).

In past efforts like the implementation of the Free Compulsory Universal Basic Education (FCUBE) programme and the Capitation Grant, these education policies aimed to unlock barriers to increasing primary school enrolment, but access to quality secondary education has been inconsistent and inequitable. With the Free Senior High School policy in 2017, the Government of Ghana provided subsidies to remove barriers to secondary schooling such as tuition, textbooks, meals, accommodation, and resources, allowing for greater access to secondary schooling (Tamanja & Pajibo, 2019).

The Free SHS policy has increased access to high school for children, particularly for children of low-income families worrying about school fees, and for those in rural areas (Shamo, 2023). This is a critical question to consider: has the Free SHS policy created equity in access to high school, or simply increased high school numbers without an eye towards other forms of exclusion?

The study will investigate the following research questions:

- In what ways does the Free SHS policy promote social justice in access, quality, and outcomes?
- What are the perceptions of the key stakeholders about the Free SHS policy on historically marginalized groups?

By discussing experiences with students, parents, teachers and administrators, this study will provide an empirical perspective of how a nationalist education policy is realized in practice in school every day, and if it will help students to achieve equitable and inclusive goals..

2. Conceptual and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Nancy Fraser's Social Justice Framework

Educational justice is more than the accessibility of education—it implicates the equity of the resource distribution, the respect for diverse identities and the inclusiveness of decision-making processes. For education to be just, it must attend to structural inequalities (Gewirtz, 1998), but also cultural exclusion (Tikly & Barrett, 2011) and mirror the diversity in society (Unterhalter, 2007). Nancy Fraser's social justice framework provides a useful lens for examining how policies such as Ghana's Free SHS initiative—with its promise of universal secondary education—promote, or fail to promote, these goals. There also is a critique of the economics of justice (Fraser, 2003) She articulates a broader perspective composed of three interlinked dimensions: **redistribution, recognition and representation**. To her mind, all three need to work together to remedy both material disadvantage and social exclusion. The usefulness of this framework lies in that it can assess whether public policies indeed mitigate inequality or reproduce it by design and unintended consequence (Fraser & Honneth, 2003; Fraser, 2005). When we apply it to education, Fraser's model broadens our scope beyond whether students are in school at all. It invites us to think about whether they're included, respected and heard. It uses her framework to explore the Free SHS policy in terms of what it offers materially, how it recognizes student identities, and whether there is an input on how the policy is developed from stakeholders.

2.1.1 Redistribution: Addressing Economic Barriers

Redistribution means ensuring the allocation of material resources that will encourage the academic aspirations of students living in poverty. In schools, that involves abolishing fees,

constructing infrastructure, hiring qualified educators, and supplying learning tools (Tikly & Barrett, 2011). The Free SHS policy is clearly redistributive—by eliminating major financial burdens, it opens the gates of senior high school to a greater number of children from less affluent homes. Fraser’s concept of redistribution also considers whether resources are shared equitably between regions and schools, however. While access has improved, however, many rural schools still lack basic facilities and sufficient teachers, critics contend (Ansah, 2020; Essuman, 2019). So the central question is not just how many students are in school, but whether all of them are getting the support they need to thrive — no matter where they live.

2.1.2 Recognition: Respecting Identity and Diversity

Recognition is about validating the identities and lived experiences of students from marginalized communities. It means schools actually must do more than simply not be discriminating; schools must actively ensure that difference in gender identity is a welcome (Fraser & Honneth, 2003; Young, 1990). For girls in Ghana, who face early marriage and domestic responsibilities, as well as for students with disabilities, who face physical and learning-related obstacles (Rolleston, 2011; Akyeampong, 2009), this is particularly urgent. Recognition prompts policymakers to consider: Are we building learning spaces where all students are seen, safe and supported? We need to assess the Free SHS policy not only on the basis of how many students it brings into the system, but on whether it actually supports those who are from backgrounds who have long been excluded from formal education.

2.1.3 Representation: Inclusion in Decision-Making

Representation concerns whose voices shape policies and decisions. In education, this implies that teachers, students, parents, and community members should be included in designing and implementing how reforms will take place (Fraser, 2005; Levinson, 2011). For the Free SHS policy, such a dimension matters because top-down decision-making can often overlook the realities on the ground faced by schools. When local voices are left out, policies

may look good on paper, but may be ineffective in practice, or fail due to a lack of local ownership (Tamanja & Pajibo, 2019). Fraser will not confess that justice is only what comes on one end of the transaction but that it's also who and what is engaged in it. We are able to explore this Free SHS policy in a much more holistic way because we are using Fraser's framework. It is so much more than statistics, whether students have the opportunity to succeed, if their identities are valued, and whether they and their communities are being heard. This multidimensional approach is critical in determining if the policy is just in practice—not merely in theory.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Global Perspectives on Free Secondary Education

Scepticism of the worth of free secondary education in many Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) is grounded in notions about exercise of fee removal and the relation it may have on access, equity, and wider national development goals. It is clear that the reforms increased enrolments. However, research has shown that free education is neither synonymous with equity nor guarantees improvement to quality (Lewin, 2009; World Bank, 2020; World Bank, 2023).

For example, the experience of countries such as Uganda, Kenya, and Sri Lanka illustrates that free secondary education policies have expanded access, but often failed to address underlying inequities. In Uganda and Kenya, enrolment increased substantially after the introduction of the policy reforms, but continued issues with overcrowded classrooms and a lack of funding, and variations across regions and districts persisted (Ssewamala et al., 2011; Oketch & Rolleston, 2007). If we consider Sri Lanka which is often admired for having free secondary education for a long time, the system also criticises unequal distribution of resources across provinces (Little, 2010; Arunatilake & Jayawardena, 2010). All three of these examples suggest

that the abolition of fees alone will not eradicate systemic injustices without dedicated investment into quality and inclusion.

These global cases suggest that the increase of access without addressing structural inequities can lead to deeper exclusion without intention. Researchers are therefore advocating for a shift toward an equity model of reform that challenges our thinking beyond access and enrolments statistics and considers and addresses the numerous social, cultural, and economic constraints faced by disadvantaged population groups (Unterhalter et al., 2014; Tikly & Barrett, 2011). This shift is in alignment with a wider understanding of inclusion, where being 'in' school is only one aspect, but being supported to succeed and bound to thrive is where the value lies.

3.2 Educational Inequality in Ghana

In Ghana, access to get an education has been historically determined by history, geography and socio-economic background. For instance, in (1995) the adoption of the FCUBE (Free Compulsory, Universal Basic Education) and Capitation Grant in (2005) were among similar reforms that sought to increase access to education at this level (Akyeampong, 2009; Rolleston, 2011), particularly in poorer communities. But there are problems, especially in secondary education. Historically, access to SHS has (founded on social and geography factors) favoured predominately the richer, urban populations. Students who reside in rural areas attend under-resourced schools with poor infrastructure and a high number of teacher shortages with most especially students in Northern Ghana (Essuman, 2019; Tamanja & Pajibo, 2019). Statistics of challenges that remote students- especially students with disabilities- face are compounded due to cultural norms affecting girls education (UNICEF, 2021). While the Free SHS initiative was an effective first step to creating equitable access by abolishing fees, there remains a dearth of evidence that shows regards to indirect costs such as transportation, uniforms, and supplies (Ansah, 2020; Shamo, 2023), which continue to limit many families from sending their child

to school. Further, a rapid increase to enrolment numbers has placed great pressures and strains on the infrastructure of the schools and personnel, particularly from under-performing schools (Edwards & Amoah, 2020) What this reveals is that firms and policy intent do not always align with the lived experience of those on the ground. Eliminating fees is essential, of course, but true equity also means tackling the other challenges students face each day trying to get to school, stay in school, and learn once they get there.

3.3 Gaps in Existing Research: Why a Social Justice Lens Matters

Most free SHS policy research so far has focused on quantitative indicators — how many students enrol in schools, pass exams, and the levels of funding provided (Tamanja & Pajibo, 2019; Ministry of Education, 2021). These numbers are significant but they fail to capture how people really experience the policy — especially in under-resourced schools and marginalized communities. There seems to be a dearth of qualitatively and theoretically informed studies which investigate what the policy looks like in practice. We know relatively little about how students, parents and teachers navigate the policy, or whether it's equally effective for everyone. Closing this gap is crucial, especially since the global education systems are currently urged to strengthen inclusion, fairness and participation (UNESCO GEM Report, 2023; Unterhalter, 2007). Drawing from Nancy Fraser's social justice framework, this study does not stop at enrolment figures — it asks much more incisive questions: Is education free, and just? Does everyone see themselves and is everyone being supported? Does this allow stakeholders to have a voice in the process? So the study adds to a growing number of scholarship seeing education reform not as simply a technical matter, but rather one of justice. It demands a more participatory, multidimensional approach — an approach that places the people most affected by policy decisions at the center.

So far, most research on the Free SHS policy has focused on quantitative indicators—how many students are enrolled, how many pass exams, and how much funding is allocated (Tamanja & Pajibo, 2019). These numbers matter, but they don't capture how people actually experience the policy—especially those in under-resourced schools and marginalized communities.

4. Methodology

4.1 Research Design and Philosophical Orientation

The study employed a qualitative research design that was informed by an interpretivist epistemology. That is, the objective wasn't to measure or quantify, but rather to explore how individuals experience the Free SHS policy in their daily lives (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018). In educational research, especially at the level of education systems in socially complex contexts such as Ghana, it is important to understand how different people decode and respond to policies based at their lived realities. An interpretivist approach enabled the study to focus on how the participants constructed meanings surrounding their experiences, and how the larger scales of policy intersect with local situations. It also fit well with the social justice focus of the research, particularly Nancy Fraser's framework, which highlights the importance of voice, recognition, and participation.

4.2 Case Study Approach and Site Selection

To investigate the everyday experiences of the Free SHS policy, this study employed a single case study design. In particular, the research was situated within one public Senior High School in Northern Ghana, a region that has a long history of education disadvantage (Yin, 2014). Case studies are particularly useful in examining complex phenomena in their real-life contexts, which are influenced by many interacting factors. Northern Ghana was purposely chosen as a site because of its acute equity difficulties, including chronic resource shortages,

higher rates of poverty, and consistently lower academic outcomes relative to southern Ghana (Ghana Statistical Service, 2022; Rolleston, 2011).

The single case design allowed an in-depth and context-rich inquiry into how equity and justice are experienced at the school level with the Free SHS policy. The school context captured the major issues that the policy aims to address—making it a theoretically and practically relevant site. As Yin (2014) argue, a single case study that is well-chosen can produce strong lessons for understanding broader implications of policy that affect schools, especially if it is a typical or a critical case within a system of cases.

4.3 Participants and Sampling Strategy

Purposive sampling was used to recruit those who would provide diverse information in relation to the research aims. The study involved 24 participants. There were 3 school heads, 6 teachers, 10 students, 3 parents, and 2 policy actors. The diversity of participants takes into account multiple perspectives on the implementation of the Free SHS policy and its perceived impacts. The research remained true to its social justice framework (Patton, 2015) by centering on those closest to the policy.

4.4 Data Collection Methods

Data were collected using semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs). The semi-structured format allowed for flexibility — participants could speak freely, but key themes were still addressed consistently across groups. Types of questions in the interview guides included: Access and financial barriers; Learning and teaching conditions; Inclusion and exclusion; Stakeholders involvement in the policy. All interviews lasted for 40–60 minutes, were held in a closed setting bearing in mind safeguarding issues especially with students, and were audio-recorded with the participant’s approval. Local languages were utilized where needed to make participants comfortable and ensure clarity. Focus group discussions with

students, teachers, and parents were conducted respectively. Groups each consisted of 5 to 6 participants and sessions took about 90 minutes. The FGDs provided great value in extracting general experiences and showing commonalities and differences for agreements. (Morgan, 1997). A local aide interpreted as needed.

4.5 Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to stringent ethical standards. All participants provided informed consent, and parental permission was secured for students under the age of 18. Participants were assured that there was no consequence to withdrawing at any time and that they would remain anonymous and that responses would be confidential. The study received Institutional Review Board of the University of Cape Coast, Ghana (IRB-UCC) approval, and efforts were made to ensure a comfortable environment—especially students, for whom the researcher took particular care to ensure a nonjudgmental, nonpunitive atmosphere in which the participants could speak freely without fear of repercussion.

4.6 Data Analysis

The data were analyzed thematically following the six phases of the (Braun & Clarke, 2006) framework: Familiarization with the data, Generating initial codes, Searching for themes, Reviewing themes, Defining and naming themes and Writing up the findings. Analyses took an inductive and deductive approach. Fraser's framework gave us such a starting point (for example, enabling us to look for themes around redistribution, recognition and representation) but also left open the space to allow new themes to emerge based on what participants said. The data were organized and managed using NVivo 14 software. Doing so helped keep things transparent and made it easy to trace development of the analysis.

4.7 Trustworthiness and Credibility

To ensure the trustworthiness of the study, member checking, peer debriefing and triangulation method were used between the groups of participants. Key findings were checked with a subset of participants through the member checking process. Peer debriefing meetings with researchers were conducted to explore biases and interpretations. Triangulation enabled verification of themes from multiple stakeholder perspectives, and strengthened the validity and rigor of the analysis (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

5. Findings

5.1 Access and Equity

Across the board, participants acknowledged that the policy on Free SHS has increased the number of students, especially those from poor and rural backgrounds, to attend SHS. For many families, it has removed a decades-old financial burden of paying school fees. As one parent put it:

“Before this policy, I was forced to pick which of my children would get to go to school. Now they all have a chance.” Students were also thankful to the policymakers for the opportunity.

A girl in SHS 2 shared:

“If school weren’t free, I would already have been married. “They gave me a future with this policy.”

Though tuition fees, admission fees, examination fees, and textbooks are covered respectively, hidden costs remain for families. Parents said they did not have money for transportation and other expenses before their wards could attend school. As a district director of education put it:

“School is free, yes — but parents still pay in other ways, and for some, things are still too much for them.”

Due to the increase in enrolment, some students are also now being placed in schools far from home, which has resulted in long travel times or a move away from home, especially in rural areas. This makes it harder for families to aid them, and introduces new risks to girls in particular. What emerges is a portrait of uneven access. The policy hasn’t opened this door wider for anyone to walk through; it just cracked it open a little further. In Fraser’s terms, redistribution has happened, but a real equity of access is still out of reach for many. Meanwhile, limited school placements due to a surge in enrollment have forced some students to attend far-off schools, uprooting family support structures and heightening vulnerability, particularly for girls. As a result, these challenges have made it clear that although redistribution has taken place, equity of access is patchy and uneven in geographic coverage.

5.2 Quality of Education

Concerns about declining quality have risen as enrolment has spiked. Teachers, in particular, described the toll of overcrowded classrooms, tight resources, and heavy workloads. One teacher said:

“I teach over 70 students now, in a class that’s designated for 35. It’s extremely hard to get a handle on, let alone teach well.”

Necessities such as textbooks, equipment for science labs, and even chalk were said to be in short supply. Students observed the difference as well. One SHS student explained:

“Sometimes, we copy notes throughout the day because there aren’t adequate resources or time to have a proper lesson.”

Such a deterioration of conditions disproportionately disadvantages rural schools, which were already under-resourced from the beginning. The Rep for ministry of education commented as below:

“Some schools can take in the additional students. Others were already having a hard time, and now they’re inundated.”

This redistribution has boosted access, but the failure to invest in infrastructure and staff has meant quality trade-offs. This shows a brittle form of justice — one that makes room for students in the classroom, if not always an opportunity to learn in a meaningful way.

5.3 Infrastructure and Resource Allocation

One of the key issues for stakeholders was the uneven distribution of infrastructure and resources. Government attention has also focused on urban schools, particularly well-endowed ones—lots of buildings, science labs, ICT centres. But rural schools, especially in the north, lag. A headteacher shared:

“We’ve got more students but no more classrooms. Some days, students learn under trees.”

In these settings, broken furniture, unreliable electricity, and no access to clean water were common problems. Teachers also observed that newer schools, or those in political strongholds, tend to be better supported, even if their needs are less urgent.

“The support is not being directed to where it’s needed most,” one teacher said. “It feels political.”

This speaks directly to Fraser’s idea of misaligned redistribution — resources are being shared, but not in the way that addresses historical disadvantage. If turned upside down, the policy could end up reinforcing the chasm between the privileged and the underserved, uncorrected.

5.4 Recognition and Inclusion

The Free SHS policy has eased attendance for many students, but it’s not enough to help those challenged by deeper barriers. Girls, students with disabilities, and learners from marginalised ethnic groups continue to face major challenges. Many girls drop out before finishing SHS,

teachers noted, not due to school fees, but because of early marriage, pregnancy, and pressure to help at home. One female teacher observed:

“The policy brings them in, but it doesn’t retain them. When the trouble arrives, the girl is removed. No support. No second chances.”

Students with disabilities are relegated to even further exclusion. Many schools are not accessible, and few teachers are trained in inclusive education. One parent of a visually impaired student said:

“There are no ramps, braille books, or special teachers. They instructed us to take my child to a special school.”

These stories show a lack of recognition, not just in a symbolic way, but in substantive educational support. As Fraser puts it, justice is about something more than equal treatment; it’s about recognizing difference and responding to it. When policies ignore what certain groups need, they reinforce rather than reduce exclusion.

5.5 Representation and Participation

One of the most conspicuous gaps in the policy’s design is the absence of stakeholder input. Teachers, parents and even some school heads said they felt like they were being told what to do, not consulted. A teacher explained:

“Decisions are made in Accra. We just get circulars. Nobody asks us what we think or what we need. Parents were equally frustrated, too. A mother from a farming area said:

“They say it’s free, but they don’t ask what we go through. “We have opinions, but we’re not at the table.”

This feeling of exclusion reflects what Fraser terms misrepresentation — being left out of decision-making spaces that affect you directly. Although the policy is ostensibly intended to benefit all Ghanaians, many believe they have no genuine input into its design or implementation. Interestingly, in a few better-resourced schools, parents and teachers

described more open communication with district authorities. But this was the exception, not the rule — and it relied heavily on local leadership. The wider pattern is just as clear: representation is weak and spotty, and without stronger pathways for participation, there's a danger that a policy will be detached from the realities it seeks to address. These combined findings highlight that although Free SHS has achieved valuable strides in access, it is still lacking in the realms of inclusion and voice. True justice, as Fraser reminds us, demands attention not only to what people have, but also to how they are viewed and whether they are heard.

6 Discussion

This research provides a nuanced exploration of the complexity of the Free SHS policy in Ghana. The policy does indeed expand access to secondary education, particularly for rural and low-income students. However, it clearly shows how layered, multidimensional, and nuanced the issue of educational justice is. This analysis illustrates the policy's successes and challenges, using Fraser's (2003) concepts of redistribution, recognition, and representation.

6.1 Partial Redistribution: Access without Adequate Resources

One of the most obvious successes of the Free SHS policy is the redistribution of access. By abolishing fees, meals, and accommodation charges, the policy has allowed many students the opportunity to attend secondary school, who otherwise would not have been able to. Free secondary education policies have led to increases in enrolment in countries like Kenya and Uganda (Lewin, 2009; Oketch & Rolleston, 2007). However, as Fraser (2003) cautions us, redistribution is about more than opening access; it is at least about ensuring equitable access to what is on the other side of the door. In Ghana, the Free SHS policy has not changed the disparities that exist at different institutions. Urban schools are often better equipped, while rural schools have large classrooms with minimal teaching material and poor infrastructure

(Essuman, 2019; Ansah, 2020). This indicates that students may attend school, without the support and connections to be effective. In short, as Darling-Hammond (2010) makes the case for equity beyond access, it lies also in strategic investments in teacher learning opportunities, the quality of instruction, and inclusive learning environments that meet all learners needs, specifically those who normally do not get that treatment.

6.2 Incomplete Recognition: Exclusion through Invisibility

Fraser's second element - recognition - uses whether schools endorse and take action based on the needs of all learners in their differences. This is where the weakness lies in policy. While the Free SHS Policy appears to be universal, it fails to consider the lived experiences of girls, the disabled, and groups that maintain exclusion based on historical positions. Girls continue to experience social expectations such as, for example, early marriage, or other forms of gendered violence, and very rarely do they see some form of official support offered to them at school. Students with disabilities remain largely invisible - not due to a lack of opportunity - but because the Ghanaian system has not been designed for them. Tikly and Barrett (2011) state that education systems that ignore identity and diversity, and privilege one group over others by doing so, replicate patterns of marginalization even while access might be increasing for students. The Free SHS Policy is also somewhat of a one-size-fits-all measure. Unless there is an explicit recognition of diversity implicit in teacher training, school organization, and curriculum, inclusion will continue to be only something aspirational, instead of realized.

6.3 Weak Representation: Centralized Governance and Silenced Voices

The third dimension, representation, refers to who gets to write the rules. Here, the evidence is decisive: the vast majority of stakeholders, particularly those outside the urban areas, believe they are being cut out of the decision-making process. Teachers and parents described the policy as something done to them, not something they helped shape or improve. The absence of local presence tends to lead to a misalignment between national objectives and local

realities. For instance, lack of consultation between school heads over how many students they can realistically absorb results in overcrowded schools and frustration. Such a top-down approach undermines the effectiveness of the policy as well as its legitimacy (Fraser, 2005; Levinson, 2011). The lack of stakeholder input is not simply an implementation problem; it's also a justice problem because educational justice includes political voice. If the policy is to succeed in the long run, those who live with its consequences need to be part of the conversation.

6.4 Global Similarities and Comparisons

Such findings are not unique to the context here but have been similarly reported within middle-income and low-income countries where free education policies on paper have not resulted in equitable outcomes. Examples from Kenya's day school policy, Uganda's capitation grant model, and Sri Lanka's regional quotas aimed to fill inequities with mixed results (Chaudhary et al., 2016; Nishimura & Ogawa, 2009). Ghana's Free SHS sets similar access goals as the foundational entrance, yet quality and context-based equity struggles are recognized. As issues of hidden costs, infrastructure, and execution bottlenecks exist, realization of social justice within education remains out of reach.

6.5 Advancing a Multidimensional Vision of Educational Justice

What FSHS demonstrates is that equality in one sense will not guarantee equality in other areas. Access is important, but it is not the end goal. If difference is not acknowledged and meaningfully represented, increasing access to education, as a way of increasing equality, may fall short; it may not enhance restorative equality or it may reproduce existing inequalities. Here, the evidence totally aligns with Fraser's position. Reimers (2020) argues that any educational reforms need to be responsive to the social context in which they operate while at the same time be globally informed in relation to inclusion and quality. Ghana's Free SHS policy, while expansive, would be more effective if it were more localized and made an effort

to engage community in making it successful. A policy can be considered successful based on enrolment figures, in the case of FSHS, but if it leaves some people behind, or fails to give a voice to others it is not a complete form of justice. The findings of this study support a more equitable paradigm - that equally values inclusion, access, and participation. Educational inequality, as Noguera (2003) reminds us, is not just about access to schools but is also a matter of structural disadvantage. Ghana's experience reflects this, where historical disparities in rural education remain despite fee-free policies. Here the view from the teacher is compelling: "The policy is a good one, but it needs to go deeper - not just students in development, but what they need to learn, to stay, and to have a voice."

7. Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to explore the experiences of key educational stakeholders - students, teachers, parents, and education adjudicators - with the Free Senior High School (FSHS) policy - at a time when they had historically limited access to educational opportunity. More generally, this study was guided by Nancy Fraser's (2003) conception of justice related to education, including an interest in redistribution, recognition and representation, in order to go beyond considerations of access to interrogate how the policy was addressing educational justice.

The study identified a number of areas where the FSHS policy has made commendable strides in addressing financial barriers to educational access; however it has not been as successful in providing equitable or inclusive outcomes for all students. The study acknowledges persistent challenges relating to overcrowded classrooms, inequitable distribution of resources, high levels of dropout for female students, exclusion of the needs and voices of students with disabilities, and exclusion of key stakeholders from decision-making processes as critical limitations to the implementation of the policy.

In conclusion, access does not equate with justice. An equitable education policy must allow all like students to access the education system; however, it must also allow for participation in the provision of supports to allow for success, and representation within the system. Justice must include fair student enrolment numbers, but must extend beyond that to how the students are experiencing their reality, how schools are responding to those students, and how they are reflecting on this policy as part of their inclusive strategy.

8. Recommendations

In order to realise the full potential of the FSHS policy to deliver comprehensive social justice in education well beyond its short-term access impact, this study delivers the following detailed recommendations:

- **Enhance equity through targeted resource allocation.**

Literally invest more money and resources in under-resourced schools, especially in rural communities. This would entail the provision of adequate classrooms, science laboratories, textbooks, ICT tools, and boarding to address overcrowding and infrastructure deficits

- **Promote inclusive education for all learners.**

Integrate gender-sensitive strategies and disability-inclusive approaches into the policy framework. These include building schools that are accessible, equipping students with special needs with the necessary devices and support personnel, and mentorship programmes to save girls vulnerable to early marriage and dropping out of school.

- **Institutionalize participatory stakeholder engagement.**

Implement inclusive governance structures at the school level, like community-based management committees, allowing for meaningful participation of parents, teachers, and students in decision-making. This helps in establishing structures like channels that

drive feedback, transparency and accountability for effective implementation of FSHS at the local level.

- **Expand and strengthen teacher recruitment, training, and support.**

Employ more trained teachers in underperforming schools, ensure continuous professional development and in-service training in schools, with incentives for teachers deployed to rural areas.

- **Develop a robust monitoring and evaluation (M&E) framework focused on equity indicators.**

Design and implement M&E system to track enrollment numbers but also quality indicators (e.g., Student-teacher ratios, infrastructure quality, learning outcomes, inclusion of marginalized groups). Embed participatory approaches to capturing community voice to inform assessments of the policy's impact.

Free SHS in Ghana can become a significant vehicle of social change. But for that to be fulfilled, it needs to become more than a way to reduce costs — it needs to be a complete equity strategy. That requires looking beyond students as mere numbers and recognizing them as unique individuals with varying needs, strengths, and stories. While Justice in education isn't just about the door being open. It's about ensuring that every student who enters it has the tools, support, and voice to succeed.

Data Availability Statement

Due to the sensitive nature of this study, participants did not consent to public sharing of their data. The data supporting this article's findings are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. However, the data are not publicly available as they contain information that could compromise the privacy and confidentiality of research participants.

Competing Interests Disclosure: The authors declare that there are no financial or non-financial competing interests related to this research.

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